

Antibacterial activity of *N*-bromonicotinamide

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Abstract : A new oxidant, *N*-bromonicotinamide was synthesized and screened for antibacterial activity in nutrient glucose agar medium disc diffusion method. The bacterial species used were *Bacillus subtilis*, *Clostridium butyricum*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Commercial Amikacin (AK) 30 µg disc was used as positive control and the zone of inhibition was measured in mm and compared with the control. The experiment was carried out in triplicate for all concentrations. *N*-Bromonicotinamide showed significant antibacterial activity and can be utilized in new antibacterial formulations.

Keywords : *N*-Bromonicotinamide, antibacterial activity, disc diffusion method, zone of inhibition.

Introduction

The discovery and development of antibiotics are among the most successful achievements of modern science and technology for the control of infectious diseases. The interesting numbers of microbes that are resistant to the commonly used therapeutic agents is a major worldwide problem to control the microorganisms. For these reasons the search for new antimicrobial agents with novel modes of action represents a major target in recent research¹.

Structurally similar, biologically active compounds containing heteroatoms have been synthesized and screened for antimicrobial activities viz. pyrimidines and related nitrogen heterocyclic rings², 6-(2-hydroxy phenyl)-4-(substituted phenyl)-3-oxo-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1*H*-indazoles³, 1-cyclo-propyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-[chloro/1-piperazinyl/4-methyl-1-piperazinyl/4-ethyl-1-piperazinyl/4-hydroxyethyl-1-piperazinyl/imidazolyl/morpholinyl]-3-[*N*-(substituted phenylamino)carbonyl]quinoline⁴, isatinones A and B, oxindole alkaloids⁵, nitrofurans⁶, 4-aminopyridinium salts⁷, isatin and its derivatives⁸, 2-aryldene-1-benzosuberone their dibromide and their pyrazoline derivatives⁹, Schiff bases derived from 4-aminobenzoic acid¹⁰, furopyrimidines and imidazopyrazolopyrimidine¹¹, pyrrolidinedione derivative¹², 1,2,4-triazoles¹³, *N*-{4-[3-(4-chlorophenyl)-oxiranecarbonyl]-

phenyl]-2-(1,1,3-trioxo-1,3-dihydrobenzo[*d*]isothiazol-2-yl)acetamide¹⁴, sulfamethoxazole¹⁵, 3-hydroxy-6-methyl-4-oxo-4*H*-pyran-2-carboxamide¹⁶, zinc(II) carboxylates with/without *N*-donor organic ligands¹⁷, nitro- and halogeno-substituted benzimidazole derivatives¹⁸, quinolones¹⁹, *N*-chlorotaurine-sodium²⁰, 3-hydrazinonaphthaquinones²¹, triazinoquinazolinones, triazepinoquinazolinones and triazocinoquinazolinones²².

N-Bromo compounds are synthesized, characterized and used as versatile reagents in kinetic studies and organic synthesis. The compound NBN offers many advantages like easy method of synthesis, low cost, easy handling, low toxicity and mild nature with appreciable stability²³. The present study is aimed at to test the *N*-bromo compound as antibacterial agents as well as to determine the optimum concentration as antibacterial agent.

Results and discussion

The antibacterial activity of *N*-bromonicotinamide was illustrated in Table 1. The bacterium *Bacillus subtilis* showed a minimum inhibition zone of 7.5 mm diameter at 50 ppm concentration and a maximum inhibition zone of 18.0 mm diameter from 750 and 1000 ppm concentrations. The other higher concentrations of NBN viz. 1250 and 1500 ppm have shown slight decline in the inhibition activity. Hence the optimum level of maximum antibacte-

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN)

Bacterial species	Inhibition zone - Diameter (mm) in different concentrations (ppm)									
	Control	50	100	250	500	750	1000	1250	1500	
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	18.0 ± 0.4082	7.5 ± 0.4082	9.0 ± 0.8164	9.0 ± 0.8164	9.0 ± 0.4082	18.0 ± 0.4082	18.0 ± 0.8164	15.0 ± 0.4082	15.0 ± 0.8164	15.0 ± 0.8164
<i>Clostridium butyricum</i>	18.0 ± 0.8164	10.5 ± 0.4082	10.5 ± 0.8498	10.5 ± 0.4082	11.0 ± 0.4082	11.0 ± 1.2247	11.0 ± 0.4082	12.0 ± 0.8164	12.0 ± 0.4082	12.0 ± 0.4082
<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	19.5 ± 0.4082	7.5 ± 0.4082	7.5 ± 0.4082	9.0 ± 0.4082	9.0 ± 0.8164	13.5 ± 0.4082	11.0 ± 0.4082	11.0 ± 0.8164	11.0 ± 0.4082	11.0 ± 0.4082
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	13.5 ± 0.4082	7.5 ± 0.4082	7.5 ± 0.7071	8.0 ± 0.4082	8.0 ± 0.7071	13.5 ± 0.4082	12.0 ± 0.4082	12.0 ± 0.8164	13.0 ± 0.4082	13.0 ± 0.4082
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	16.5 ± 0.4082	7.5 ± 0.4082	9.0 ± 0.4082	9.0 ± 0.8164	10.5 ± 0.4082	18.0 ± 0.8164	18.0 ± 0.4082	13.5 ± 0.8164	13.5 ± 0.4082	13.5 ± 0.4082
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	19.5 ± 0.4082	10.5 ± 0.8164	12.0 ± 0.8164	12.0 ± 1.0801	12.0 ± 0.4082	15.0 ± 0.8164	15.0 ± 0.4082	15.0 ± 0.4082	14.0 ± 0.8164	14.0 ± 0.8164

Control : Amikacin (AK) 30 µg/antibiotic disc.

rial effect of NBN for *B. subtilis* is between 750 to 1000 ppm concentrations. The control Amikacin (AK) antibiotic disc recorded 18.0 mm inhibition at 30 µg concentration. Comparatively NBN compound at 750 ppm concentration was equivalent of 30 µg of Amikacin (AK) with respect to antibacterial effect for *B. subtilis* [Fig. 1(a)].

Clostridium butyricum showed a minimum inhibition of 10.5 mm diameter at 50, 100 and 250 ppm concentrations to a maximum inhibition zone of 12.0 mm diameter at 1250 and 1500 ppm concentrations. For *C. butyricum* the antibacterial activity of NBN was directly proportional to the concentration. The control Amikacin (AK) recorded 18.0 mm inhibition at 30 µg concentration. Comparatively NBN compound was 66.6% effective for 1250 and 1500 ppm concentrations for *C. butyricum* [Fig. 1(b)].

Antibacterial activity of *E. aerogenes* revealed a minimum inhibition zone of 7.5 mm diameter at 50 and 100 ppm concentrations to a maximum inhibition zone of 13.5 mm diameter for 750 ppm concentration. The other higher concentrations of NBN i.e. 1000, 1250 and 1500 ppm showed a decline in the inhibition level. Therefore optimum level of maximum antibacterial effect of NBN for *E. aerogenes* was 750 ppm concentration. The control Amikacin (AK) antibiotic disc showed 19.5 mm inhibition at 30 µg concentration. The optimum inhibition level of NBN was comparatively 69% effective for 750 ppm concentration for *E. aerogenes* [Fig. 1(c)].

Escherichia coli tested for antibacterial activity showed a minimum inhibition zone of 7.5 mm diameter at 50 and 100 ppm concentrations. The maximum inhibition zone of 13.5 mm diameter was found to be at 750 ppm concentration. At 1000 and 1250 ppm concentrations the inhibition zone measured 12.0 mm, whereas 13.0 mm for 1500 ppm concentrations. The control Amikacin (AK) showed an inhibition zone of 13.5 mm which was equivalent to the inhibition zone of 13.5 mm by NBN [Fig. 1(d)].

P. aeruginosa revealed a minimum antibacterial activity of inhibition zone of 7.5 mm diameter at 50 ppm concentration and the maximum zone of inhibition at 750 and 1000 ppm respectively. The other higher concentrations of NBN showed a decline in the antibacterial activity i.e. 13.5 mm inhibition. The control Amikacin (AK) revealed 16.5 mm inhibition zone, it was found that NBN

is more effective for *P. aeruginosa* [Fig. 1(e)].

Staphylococcus aureus tested for antibacterial activity showed a minimum inhibition zone of 10.5 mm diameter at 50 ppm concentration. The maximum inhibition zone of 15.0 mm diameter was noticed at 750, 1000 and 1250 ppm concentrations. The control Amikacin (AK) revealed 19.5 mm inhibition zone at 30 µg concentration. The optimum inhibition level of NBN was comparatively 75% effective at 750, 1000 and 1250 ppm concentrations for *S. aureus* [Fig. 1(f)].

Fig. 1. Antibacterial activity of *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN) : (a) *Bacillus subtilis*, (b) *Clostridium butyricum*, (c) *Enterobacter aerogenes*, (d) *Escherichia coli*, (e) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, (f) *Staphylococcus aureus*; (1) 50 ppm, (2) 100 ppm, (3) 250 ppm, (4) 500 ppm, (5) 750 ppm, (6) 1000 ppm, (7) 1250 ppm, (8) 1500 ppm; (AK) Amikacin 30 mcg/disc.

The antibacterial activity against *Bacillus spp.* was reported by Sh El-Shariet²⁴. According to the report that the compounds 3-amino-2-[4-methyl phenylsulphonamidoethyl]quinazolin-4-(3*H*)-one (**3d**) and 3-amino-2-[1-

(4-methylphenylsulphonamido)-1-(isopropyl)methyl]quinazolin-4-(3*H*)-one (**3e**) compounds showed maximum antibacterial activities to *B. cereus* rather than the other compound, methyl *N*-[4'-methylphenylsulphonyl-2-phenylglycyl]anthranilate (**2b**) and *N*-[4'-methylphenylsulphonyl-β-alaninyl]anthranilate (**2d**). In the present work, the effect of NBN compound as antibacterial agent varies with the concentrations and optimum concentrations of 750 and 1000 ppm were found to show the maximum inhibition zone. The growth inhibition differed with different antibacterial agents because of the compound-cell membrane interactions.

Clostridium difficile was reported by Mahony²⁵. It was reported that the bismuth compound might serve as a potential therapeutic significance to *C. difficile* and it is to be stated that the NBN compound also effectively inhibited the growth of *C. butyricum* is yet another record of this kind of therapeutic significance.

The antibacterial activity against *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *E. colaceticus* was reported by Al-Bahtiti⁹ and according to this study, heterocyclic derivatives of chalcones-2-arylidene-1-benzosuberone, their dibromide and their pyrazoline derivatives were effective antibacterial compounds against the above mentioned bacterial species. According to Parekh¹⁰ some Schiff bases derived from 4-aminobenzoic acid exhibited antibacterial activity against *Enterobacter aerogenes* ATCC 13048. El-Sayed² reported that non-ionic surfactants containing pyrimidines and related nitrogen heterocyclic ring systems has shown antibacterial activity against *E. aerogenes*. Such reports were in line with the respect investigations with NBN compound tested against *E. aerogenes*.

The antibacterial activity of *Eshcherichia coli* to various compounds were reported by many workers. The zinc(II) carboxylates¹⁷ with the presence of *N*-donor organic ligands were found to show antibacterial activity to *E. coli*. The synthesized 3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4*H*-pyran-2-carboxamide and the amide derivatives showed antibacterial activity to *E. coli*¹⁶. According to Fuente⁶, many new antimicrobial compounds like naphthalimide, salicylanilide, bipyridinium and quinazolinodiamine showed antibacterial activity against *E. coli*. Such reports were found to be similar to the present work with *N*-bromonicotinamide compound against *E. coli*.

The antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was reported by Aytemir and Erol¹⁶. According to their study, the 3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4*H*-pyran-2-carboxamide and its amide derivatives of pyranone showed the antibacterial activity to *P. aeruginosa*. The new antimicrobial compounds like naphthalimide, salicylanilide, bipyridinium and quinazolinediamine were found to show antibacterial activity for *P. aeruginosa*⁶. According to their report such new antimicrobial compound were needed because of the emergence of microbes that were resistant to available antibiotics. The *N*-bromonicotinamide compound tested for the present work showed a good result at an optimum concentration of 750 and 1000 ppm, hence NBN is yet another report of new antimicrobial compound to *P. aeruginosa*.

The antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* showed a maximum inhibition response to 3-amino-2-[1-(4-methylphenylsulphonamido)-1-(iso-propyl)methyl]-quinazolin-4-(3*H*)-one (**3e**) and 3-amino-2-[1-(4-methylphenylsulphonamido)-1-(iso-butyl)methyl]-quinazolin-4-(3*H*)-one (**3f**), ethyl-1-(oxo-5,11-dihydro-[1,2,4]triazepino compounds and a minimum inhibition response to methyl *N*-[4'-methylphenylsulphonyl-β-alaninyl]anthranilate (**2d**) compound. Aytemir⁸ reported that *S. aureus* exhibited higher antibacterial activity to 3-hydroxy-6-methyl-4-oxo-4*H*-pyran-2-[*N*-(4'-methyl-coumarin-7-yl)carboxamide] (**8c**) compound. Zelank¹⁹ also reported the antibacterial activity of zinc(II) carboxylates with the presence of *N*-donor organic ligands to *S. aureus*. The present investigation with NBN compound is an additional source of information as antibacterial compound to *S. aureus*.

Experimental

Materials :

The bacterial species tested for the present study have been obtained from the microbial culture collection centre, Department of Botany (Microbiology Unit), National College, Tiruchirappalli.

Methods :

The antibacterial activity of *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN) was conducted using Nutrient Glucose Agar medium²⁹ (Hi-media). The medium was sterilized in an autoclave at 121 °C for 20 min. Then it was allowed to cool to 50 °C and poured in sterile Petri dishes to solidify at room temperature.

Antibacterial assay by disc diffusion method :

Various concentrations viz. 50, 100, 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1250 and 1500 ppm of *N*-bromonicotinamide were tested for antibacterial activity by the disc diffusion method as described by Prescott³⁰. The bacterial strains were individually streaked uniformly all over the Nutrient Agar medium in 9.0 cm Petri dishes. The plain sterile disc (Himedia SD067) was loaded with different concentrations of *N*-bromonicotinamide. The commercial Amikacin (AK) 30 µg disc was used as control at the end of 48 h; the zone of bacterial growth inhibition was measure in mm and compared with control. The petridisc were incubated at 37 ± 1 °C, the experiment was carried out in triplicate for all the bacterial species.

Conclusion :

The *N*-halo compound *N*-bromonicotinamide was screened for antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Clostridium butyricum*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed the maximum level of inhibition of growth at optimum concentrations. *N*-Bromonicotinamide is found to be bacteriocidal in nature.

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